

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino-a-pyrone and Furocoumarins. Part IX*: Synthesis of 2-Methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo (3,2-c) benzopyrans

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4-Allyloxy coumarin derivatives (II), when subjected to Claisen rearrangement gave 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran derivatives (III). These on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (10%) afforded the corresponding 2-methyl-4-oxo-4H(3,2-c)benzopyran derivatives (IV).

In recent years the importance of *o*-hydroxyallyl coumarins has been increased because of the fact that these can be used as starting materials for the synthesis of 2-substituted furocoumarins¹ as well as unsubstituted furocoumarins² which occur in nature. It has been suggested by Chmielewska and Cieslak³ that structure (I) is essential for the anticoagulant activity in 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives. It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the Claisen rearrangement of different 4-allyloxy coumarin derivatives and convert them to 2-methyl-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran derivatives (IV).

4-Hydroxycoumarin on allylation with allyl bromide gave 4-allyloxy coumarin (IIa) which on Claisen rearrangement gave an alkali insoluble product to which 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIIa) structure is assigned; 4-hydroxy-3-allyl coumarin could not be isolated from the reaction mixture. IIIa on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (10%) gave 2-methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVa).

I

- II. a. $R = R_1 = R_2 = H$
 b. $R = CH_3; R_1 = R_2 = H$
 c. $R = R_2 = H; R_1 = OCH_3$
 d. $R = H; R_1 = OCH_3; R_2 = CH_3$
 e. $R = H; R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$

- III a. $R = R_1 = R_2 = H$
 b. $R = CH_3; R_1 = R_2 = H$
 c. $R = R_2 = H; R_1 = OCH_3$
 d. $R = H; R_1 = OCH_3; R_2 = CH_3$
 e. $R = H; R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$

- IV a. $R = R_1 = R_2 = H$
 b. $R = CH_3; R_1 = R_2 = H$
 c. $R = R_2 = H; R_1 = OCH_3$
 d. $R = H; R_1 = OCH_3; R_2 = CH_3$
 e. $R = H; R_1 = R_2 = OCH_3$

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Similarly 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin⁴, 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin⁵, 4-hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin⁶ and 4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin⁷ on allylation gave 4-allyloxy-6-methylcoumarin (IIb), 4-allyloxy-7-methoxycoumarin (IIc), 4-allyloxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin (II d) and 4-allyloxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (IIe) respectively. These allyloxy coumarins on Claisen rearrangement gave corresponding dihydrofurocoumarin derivatives (III) which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal gave 2,8-dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVb), 2-methyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVc), 2,6-dimethyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVd) and 2-methyl-6,7-dimethoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVe) respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Allyloxy coumarin (IIa): A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (5.0 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (6.0 g.), allyl bromide (4.0 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 20 hrs. The product which was obtained on evaporation of acetone was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 115°. Yield 3.0 g. (Found: C, 71.03; H, 4.94. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.99%).

2-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIIa): 4-Allyloxy coumarin (2.0 g.) was heated at 210–20° in an oil bath for 2 hrs. After cooling, the product was washed with petroleum ether and purified by passing its solution in benzene over alumina. The product, obtained after the evaporation of the solvent, crystallised from ether petroleum m.p. 100°. Yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 71.03; H, 4.64. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.99%).

2-Methyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVa): IIIa (0.5 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.3 g.; 10%) in boiling diphenyl ether (4 ml.) for 8 hrs. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and allowed to cool. The separated product was filtered, washed with ether petroleum and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 174°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 71.81; H, 4.09. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 71.99; H, 4.03%).

4-Allyloxy-6-methylcoumarin (IIb): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (5.0 g.), allyl bromide (3 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (6.0 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) on a water bath for 25 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 108°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 72.02; H, 5.38. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.21; H, 5.59%).

2,8-Dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IIIb) 4-Allyloxy-6-methylcoumarin (1.0 g.) was heated at 200° in an oil bath for 2 hrs. After cooling, the product was washed with ether-petroleum and purified by passing over alumina. The purified product crystallised from ether-petroleum, m.p. 111°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 72.33; H, 5.92. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.21; H, 5.59%).

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2,8-Dimethyl-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVb): 2,8-Dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (0.4 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.39; 10%) in boiling diphenyl ether (2 ml.) for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 155°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 72.86; H, 4.67. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72.89; H, 4.71%).

4-Allyloxy-7-methoxycoumarin (IIc): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxycoumarin (5.0 g.), allyl bromide (3 ml.) and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (6.0 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (60 ml.) on a water bath for 20 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the product crystallised from ether-petroleum, m.p. 114°. Yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 67.07; H, 5.37. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

2-Methyl-7-methoxy-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (IIIc): 4-Allyloxy-7-methoxycoumarin (1.2 g.) was heated at 200–10° in an oil bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and worked up as described above. The product crystallised from ether-petroleum, m.p. 106°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.70; H, 5.20. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.21%).

2-Methyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVc): 2-Methyl-7-methoxy-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (0.5 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.4 g.; 10%) in diphenyl ether (3 ml.) for 8 hrs. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and worked up as before. The product crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 176°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 67.63; H, 4.57. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 67.82; H, 4.38%).

4-Allyloxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin (IID): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin (5.0 g.), allyl bromide (3 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (6.0 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) on a water bath for 20 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 163°. Yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 68.25; H, 5.36. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.28; H, 5.73%).

2,6-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (IIId): 4-Allyloxy 7-methoxy-8-methylcoumarin (2.0 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 210° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and worked up as usual. The product crystallised from ether-petroleum, m.p. 135°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.87; H, 5.77. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.28; H, 5.73%).

2,6-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (IVd): 2,6-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (0.5 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.4 g.; 10%) in diphenyl ether. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 155°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 68.52; H, 4.84. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 68.84; H, 4.95%).

4-Allyloxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (IIe): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (4.0 g.), allyl bromide (2.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (6.0 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 20 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual and the product crystallised from ether-petroleum, m.p. 134°. Yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 64.57; H, 5.52. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.11; H, 5.38%).

2-Methyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (IIIe): 4-Allyloxy-7,8-dimethoxycoumarin (1.5 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 210° for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and worked up as described earlier. The product crystallised from ether-petroleum, m.p. 110°. Yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 64.31; H, 5.64. C₁₄H₁₄O₅ requires C, 64.11; H, 5.38%).

2-Methyl-6,7-dimethoxy-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c) benzopyran (IVe) : 2-Methyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-dihydro-4-oxo-4H-furo(3,2-c)benzopyran (0.5 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.3 g.; 10%) in diphenyl ether (3 ml.) for 8 hrs and the reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product crystallised from dil. acetic acid, m.p. 170°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 64.18; H, 4.33. C₁₄H₁₂O₅ requires C, 64.61; H, 4.65%).

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